

Consent Form

**Please complete and return this form only if you wish to join
the SAFER Wearables Study**

Title: The SAFER Wearables Study:
A study of the acceptability and performance of wearables for
atrial fibrillation screening in older adults.

Chief Investigator: Dr Peter Charlton, University of Cambridge

IRAS Project ID: 283812 {Invite ID: XXXX}

If you are willing to take part in the SAFER Wearables Study, please read
the following statements and if you agree, initial them, and sign overleaf.

<i>Initials:</i> _____	1) I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet version 1.3, dated 7 th Feb 2024 for the above study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers and explanations provided.
<i>Initials:</i> _____	2) I understand that my participation in this study is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without my medical care or legal rights being affected.
<i>Initials:</i> _____	3) I understand that information related directly to my participation in this study may be looked at by responsible individuals from the sponsor, regulatory authorities and research personnel where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my information.
<i>Initials:</i> _____	4) I understand that my GP will be informed of my participation in this study.
<i>Initials:</i> _____	5) I understand that my anonymous study data will be shared with device manufacturers where necessary (including PulseOn in Finland), shared with others, and made publicly available.
<i>Initials:</i> _____	6) I agree to participate in this study.

By putting your initials in the boxes and signing this form you are consenting that you agree with all of the statements listed, and that the details listed below are correct.

Name of participant: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Please complete the details below in BLOCK CAPITALS. Items marked (*) are mandatory. Return this form to the study team in the prepaid envelope.

Title:
* First name:
* Last name:
* Date of birth (dd/mm/yyyy):
* Gender:
* Address:
* Postcode:
* Home Tel:
Mobile Tel: (optional)
* GP Practice name:

If you would like a copy of your consent form please contact the study team. The study team will only use these details for study purposes.

Office use Name: Signature: Date: Participant ID: